

1. SONNETS Innovation Identification Framework

1.1 Framework Overview

The SONNETS Innovation Identification Framework is an innovative methodological framework that will accelerate the transformation of the public sector into an innovation breeding carrier. The goal of the SONNETS Framework is twofold and lies in supporting innovation both **in the public sector** and **through the public sector**.

Innovation in the public sector may have an internal or external focus, pertaining to the improvement of the public sector internal processes and the former's efficiency, and the development of improved services for citizens and businesses respectively, and targets the public sector's modernization. On the other side, ***innovation through the public sector*** focuses on promoting the generation and implementation of innovative ideas and the corresponding creation of value in other sectors and pursues accordingly the transformation of the public sector into an innovation driver.

The Framework emphasizes the necessity to have an informed view of the current societal trends and challenges as a prerequisite for better accommodating the respective needs, as well as the role of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) as a key enabler for innovation, and pursues its goal by means of coupling findings on emerging ICTs and trends with insights on current societal challenges and needs. Such coupling is carried out on the basis of specifying and bringing into the foreground specific innovative solutions for the adoption of the identified technologies and the confrontation of the identified needs respectively. In this respect, the SONNETS Innovation Identification Framework, and more specifically the innovation solutions specified are considered as the means to bridge the identified needs with technologies.

The Framework does not limit though its scope in the specification of relevant innovation solutions. It further addresses the assessment and evaluation of their actual innovation potential. The latter is considered under the prism of both the impact and feasibility of the identified solutions. To this end, the Framework defines a set of impact assessment criteria and feasibility assessment criteria, in

order to evaluate the innovation potential of the solutions under consideration for the public sector. The former are used to evaluate the magnitude of the potential effects of the identified solutions, whereas the latter are employed to assess the research needs, which the technological, socio-economic and ethical implications of these solutions translate into. The rating of the specified solutions against both the dimensions of impact and feasibility allows to distinguish and, possibly prioritize, those solutions that hold greater value for the public sector, and lays the foundations for designing a concrete time plan of actions and a set of recommendations for their implementation in practice.

From a methodological point of view, the SONNETS Framework relies basically on the methods of desk-based research, interviews, focus groups and workshops, and open consultations, and encompasses six logical steps or phases as follows:

- i) the identification of societal needs, societal and public sector trends/challenges ([*Needs Identification*](#))
- ii) the identification of emerging technologies and trends that make a difference today in other sectors ([*Technology Identification*](#))
- iii) the selection of a subset of these technologies and trends, and the analysis of the latter in terms of their key characteristics and specificities ([*Technology Selection and Analysis*](#))
- iv) the assessment of these technologies in the domains originally met and their correlation to the public sector needs and societal challenges on the basis of existing services and applications, as well as new innovation solutions that may benefit from these technologies ([*Technology Assessment*](#))
- v) the evaluation of these services' and solutions' innovation potential in terms of both their impact and feasibility ([*Innovation Identification*](#))
- vi) the selection among the former, of those that make more sense to be ported to the public sector through the development of adequate scenarios ([*Scenario Building*](#))
- vii) the evaluation and ratification of the overall findings ([*Results Validation*](#)).

1.2 Framework Steps

1.2.1 Needs Identification

The identification of existing pressing or emerging societal needs, challenges and trends is a key component and prerequisite for delivering innovations that hold true value for the society; thereby, it constitutes the first step and starting point of the SONNETS Innovation Identification Framework Methodology. The latter targets more specifically to identify societal challenges and public sector needs and can be based, given the abstract and wide scope of the subject under study, on qualitative research: the latter should incorporate both a systematic literature review approach, taking into account all relevant research and scientific papers, policy documents, white papers and European Union reports, industry reports, as well as interviews and focus groups with representatives of the stakeholder groups (e.g. citizens, businesses, public sector officials and employees), the needs and requirements of which are to be determined.

These methods are intended to serve as the means to collect but also analyse, prioritize and validate targeted stakeholder needs, and thus generate a list of needs, that can be leveraged in the subsequent steps of the methodology to propose relevant innovation solutions and guide the selection of technologies. Provided that the SONNETS Innovation Framework aims at supporting ICT-driven innovation, attention is drawn to the fact that the latter pertain solely to the ICT domain; therefore the list of needs to be compiled is also to be restricted to needs that can be addressed through the adoption and use of ICT.

1.2.2 Technology Identification

The next step of the SONNETS Innovation Identification Framework Methodology is that of technology identification. This step pertains purely to the conduction of information collection activities, and thereby its nature is a preparatory one, whereas its goal is to provide a pool of emerging technologies and trends that make a difference today in other sectors.

From a methodological point of view, this step relies mainly on extensive desk-based research, and the examination thereby of a variety of information sources, including European Commission resources, research project documents and roadmaps, studies from consultancy firms and online tools, whereas it also encompasses the conduction of interviews with IT experts from the public sector and the business and research communities.

The output of this step, and thus of the aforementioned methods is a preliminary, list of technologies and technological trends, being referred to hereinafter as SONNETS long list of technologies, that is to be reviewed and refined during the subsequent steps of the methodology.

1.2.3 Technology Selection and Analysis

The preliminary long list of technologies, generated in the technology identification phase, feeds into the next step of the framework methodology, entitled as technology selection and analysis. This step targets to refine the initial list of technologies and trends, based on their relevance for the public sector, and thereby their potential adequacy to fulfil the identified societal and public sector needs, and to go a little deeper with regard to the selected items, and therefore record basic information on them, in order to create a deeper understanding of their characteristics and specificities. Such information needs to include a number of aspects as follows:

- Identifier: a unique identifier that determines the particular technology (TE#x) or technological trend (TT#x) addressed.
- Type: an indication of whether a technology or trend is a self-standing one or has resulted from the technological convergence of other fields and which these fields are.
- Description: a brief description of the scope, aims and usage of the technology / trend addressed.
- Mainstream Domains of Application: the application domains, in which a technology / trend is basically met.
- Related Market Potential / Forecasted Growth: quantitative (statistic) or qualitative information on the anticipated growth and spread of the technology / trend addressed or the potential and growth of the related market.

- **Related Terms:** a list of similar terms used to describe the particular technology / trend or to denote specific aspects of it, and that can be employed to collect further information.
- **Source(s):** a reference to the source(s) drawing attention to or pointing out the particular technology / trend as an important one for the years to come.

The methods employed in the technology selection and analysis phase include the conduction of desk-based research and interviews, as well as the organisation of focus groups, whereas its outcomes can be summarised in the compilation of a refined list of technologies and trends, hereinafter being referred to as SONNETS short list of technologies and a compendium of emerging technologies and trends, incorporating basic but quite enlightening information on the identified technologies and trends for future reference.

1.2.4 Technology Assessment

The fourth step of the SONNETS Innovation Identification Methodology maps to technology assessment. This step is intended to dive even deeper with regard to the analysis of the identified technologies and trends, targeting on the one side to assess the impact of the identified technologies and trends in the domains originally met, and to draw conclusions, on the other, with regard to their relevance for the public sector and the different policy domains. Technology assessment is intended more specifically to include a number of aspects as follows:

- **Identifier:** a unique identifier that determines the particular technology or technological trend addressed (same as in the technology analysis phase).

- **SWOT Analysis:** An adapted SWOT analysis, that will use the “Strengths” and “Weaknesses” components of the SWOT matrix to identify the impact, namely the benefits and weak points, of each identified technology / trend in the domain originally met, and the “Opportunities” and “Threats” blocks to draw high level correlations among the considered technologies and trends and the opportunities of their adoption, usage and promotion by the public sector as well as the imposed challenges and threats.
- **Relevant Needs:** a list of the societal needs that may be associated with the particular technology or trend.
- **Potential Applications / Services:** a list of existing or new services that may materialise the envisaged innovations.
- **Existing solutions / products / services:** a list of established solutions or best practices based on the specific technology or trend.

Based on the former aspects, the relevance of the identified technologies and trends to the public sector and other policy domains will take place along three levels, these of the SWOT analysis identifying opportunities and threats, the correlation with specific needs and the identification of existing or new services.

Apparently, this phase is meant to use as input both the long list and compendium of technologies as well as the confirmed and validated set of societal and public sector needs, whereas it will employ the same arsenal of methods, namely desk-based research, interviews and focus groups. On the other hand, as an outcome, it will deliver the *technology SWOT analysis* and a draft, preliminary *list of potential innovation solutions*.

1.2.5 Innovation Identification

The fifth step of the Framework Methodology pertains to technology identification and constitutes a key task in the process of transforming the public sector into an innovation breeding carrier. The focus during this step transposes from the level of technologies to the level of the innovation solutions identified and the goal is to come up with a systematic way to record and assess the innovation potential of these solutions. The latter accrues as the resultant of two basic components, namely the impact and feasibility of the identified technology solutions, which are evaluated against appropriate assessment criteria.

As far as the impact component is concerned, a number of vertical dimensions are recognised. These pertain in the case of public sector modernization to the institutional or capacity development and political domains, whereas as far as the goal of transforming the public sector into an innovation driver is concerned, these enumerate key policy domains, i.e. the economic, social, infrastructural/transport and environmental domains. Each of these domains is further being analysed accordingly in a number of lesser aspects, which map to the specific directions where the impact of the identified ICT solutions can be located. The selection of these aspects is justified in the following paragraphs.

(I) PS Modernization

➤ Institutional/ Capacity Development

- Degree of Resources (Capital, Personnel, Infrastructure) Utilization: ICTs can be used to reduce or optimize the use of another resource by a process. Such resource may be labour, capital or a natural resource (e.g. energy), i.e. some material resource. Thereby, the use of ICTs in the public sector to improve the former's operation and processes, and in this respect ICT-driven process optimization, can be seen as substituting technological knowhow (immaterial resource) and/or infrastructure (material resource) for other material resources, thus reducing the amount of resources required and/or intensifying their use.
- Efficiency / Productivity: ICTs play indisputably a major role in the improvement of public sector efficiency and productivity, as they are qualified as general purpose technologies, i.e. technologies that are pervasive and can thus be applied to several production sectors¹. As a result, their impact on the former dimensions has to be taken into account, though it may be difficult to be determined, due to the nature of the public sector operation, which is process-based, the nature of the outcomes produced (services, intangibles, often unpriced or collectively consumed), their heterogeneity, as well as due to the multiple levels of focus (e.g. government wide level,

¹ Federico Biagi (2013). ICT and Productivity: A Review of the Literature – JRC Technical Reports. Available from <http://ftp.jrc.es/EURdoc/JRC84470.pdf>

sectoral level, individual organization level) to be potentially considered.

- Sustainability: Sustainability is a direct outcome of the operation of the public sector in a way that guarantees proper fulfilment of both present and future needs. As such it is indirectly influenced by the introduction and usage of modern ICTs in view of achieving efficiency and productivity gains, ensuring optimization of the resources available and providing high quality services, as well as by the necessary provisions for their maintenance and updating.
- Cross-organization Cooperation: The purpose of implementing e-Governance (which stands for the application of ICTs in government processes), is to improve governance processes and outcomes with the view to improving the delivery of public services. Thereby, the quality of services offered to citizens and businesses is an important dimension of the technology impact assessment analysis. Improvements in the quality of public services as a result of the introduction of ICTs may take several forms, including the reduction of personal interface of citizens and businesses with public service providers or the increase in the speed of response, and the generation thus of time savings, the reduction of bureaucratic red tape and the corresponding simplification of relevant processes, the increase in the availability of public services, as well as their delivery through additional channels.
- Quality of Services Provided: In order to be effective and efficient but also to deliver citizens and businesses quality public services, public sector authorities cannot operate today isolated but need to establish cooperation among each other. ICT is a necessary condition for such cooperation, which concerns both the different levels of public administration, e.g. local, regional, national etc. as well as diverse policy domains of the same administrative level. Such cooperation further applies at the European level with the view of providing cross-border public services, supporting the rights of citizens to live and work anywhere in the Union and of businesses to offer services across the EU single market.
- Image Modernization: The image and public standing of an organization plays inevitably a major role in target audience preferences and thereby in the outcomes of the technology impact assessment analysis. Attention has to be drawn to the fact that the image of an institution is a rather elusive topic, as there is virtually no comparative research as to the level of the institution's public standing. On the other hand, the institutional quality control processes differ immensely across public sector organizations and offer no guarantee of raising public standing.

As this is nevertheless a vital aspect of institutional development, it has to be considered as a facet of impact assessment.

➤ Political

- Level of Participation: Information and communication technologies can facilitate democratic processes and increase the participation of citizens in these. Such impacts may occur as a result of greater communication and information dissemination offered by ICTs, through the use of social networking sites, e-mail and mobile phones. They are also frequently enabled by electronic information and services offered by government (e-government). Of particular interest is additionally how e-government can improve democratic processes and encourage citizen participation in decision-making and how e-participation in specific can change the dynamics between government and citizens².
- Transparency: ICT constitutes the main lever of e-government, which contributes in turn to enhancing accountability and promoting good governance in the public sector, which are thus taken as an assessment dimension under the aspect of Transparency.
- Creation of Trust & Confidence: Trust is a complex interpersonal and organizational construct³. In political terms, trust means that citizens appraise the government and its institutions, policy-making in general and/or the individual political leaders as promise-keeping, efficient, fair and honest⁴. Political trust, in other words, is the "judgment of the citizenry that the system and the political incumbents are responsive, and will do what is right even in the absence of constant scrutiny"⁵. Citizens' trust and confidence in government is influenced by several factors, including citizens' satisfaction and expectations, transparency, accountability, digital transformation of government and performance of the government⁶, all either directly or indirectly affected notably by the introduction and usage of ICTs.

² UNCTAD (2011). Measuring the Impacts of Information and Communication Technology for Development. UNCTAD Current Studies on Science, Technology and Innovation. N ° 3 Available from http://unctad.org/en/Docs/dtlstict2011d1_en.pdf

³ Duck, S. The Handbook of Personal Relationships: Theory, Research and Interventions. New York: Wiley, 1997.

⁴ Blind, P.K. (2006). Building Trust in Government in the twenty-first century: Review of Literature and Emerging Issues, UNDESA.

⁵ Miller, A. H. and O. Listhaug. "Political Parties and Confidence in Government: A Comparison of Norway, Sweden and the United States," British Journal of Political Science 20, 3 (July 1990): 357-386.

⁶ Mohamed, M. (2016). Enhancing Citizens' Trust and Confidence in Government through Digital Transformation, in IJEGR, 12(1), IGI Global.

(II) PS as an Innovation Driver

➤ Economical

- Productivity (Labour / Capital / Resource) & Growth: The impact of ICT on economic growth and productivity can be considered at the macro, sectoral and firm levels. At the microeconomic level, positive impacts of ICT can be attributed to i. the increase in the size and productivity of the ICT sector, and associated effects such as growth in industries that provide inputs to ICT production, ii. ICT investment across the economy, which contributes to capital deepening and leads to a rise in labour productivity, iii. multi-factor productivity growth across the economy, which arises from the role of ICT in helping firms innovate and improve their overall efficiency^{7, 8}. Macro-level research has generally shown a positive link between ICT investment and growth in GDP⁹. A growing ICT sector (ICT services and ICT manufacturing industries) can contribute to aggregate increases in productivity, GDP and trade. Opportunities for economic growth arise also for businesses retailing ICT goods. Enterprises in other sectors as well may benefit from the use of more sophisticated ICT applications (such as web-based e-commerce and other e-business applications). There may also be spillover benefits. For instance, ICT investment in a larger enterprise may benefit a whole sector, whereas there may furthermore be gains from ICT diffusion along the supply chain. At the firm level use of computers, the Internet and broadband have a positive relationship with productivity. However, this varies among individual businesses according to other factors, such as skills and innovation. A particular challenge of firm level studies is measuring the effect of intangibles, such as good management

⁷ OECD (2004). The Economic Impact of ICT, Measurement, Evidence and Implications. Available from <http://www.oecd.org/bookshop?pub=922004051P1>

⁸ OECD (2008). The Contribution of the ICT Sectors to Economic Growth in OECD Countries: Backward and Forward Linkages. DSTI/ICCP/IIS(2008)2.

⁹ UNCTAD (2011). Measuring the Impacts of Information and Communication Technology for Development. UNCTAD Current Studies on Science, Technology and Innovation. N ° 3 Available from http://unctad.org/en/Docs/dtistict2011d1_en.pdf

and marketing¹⁰. A number of studies have found that ICT has most impact when accompanied by complementary investments and changes, for example, in human capital, organizational change and other forms of innovation¹¹.

There is further some evidence that the development of a strong ICT sector can lead to poverty alleviation, although there are few targeted studies on this¹². The concept of poverty though extends beyond the economic dimension and can be considered along its social dimension under the aspect of well-being and prosperity. Negative economic impacts associated with ICT diffusion have received relatively little attention from statisticians. A possible indirect negative impact is a productivity trap resulting from updating ICT too frequently to enable efficiency gains.

- Entrepreneurship: The value of ICT extends far beyond direct economic benefits. ICT is a driving force in the acceleration of entrepreneurship, making it easier to identify and develop good ideas, and create and disseminate new products and services. Some of the ways in which ICT supports entrepreneurship include increasing interconnectedness and collaboration, allowing smaller, entrepreneurship companies to compete in global markets, lowering the cost of entry for new entrepreneurs, facilitating research diversification and interdisciplinary approaches, enhancing the ability of entrepreneurs to develop new business models, products, services and processes, shortening product development cycles, providing new tools to create, organize, store and transmit information, supporting disruptive business models that transform industries and enabling faster access to regional and international markets¹³.
- Innovation: Innovation is a broad concept, defined by the Oslo Manual¹⁴ as “the implementation of a new or significantly improved product (good or service), or process, a new marketing method, or a new organizational method in business practices, workplace organization or external relations”. Innovation can occur in all sectors of the economy, including government and higher education, and involves all forms of research and experimental development, as defined by the

¹⁰ UNCTAD (2007). Information Economy Report 2007–2008: Science and Technology for Development, the New Paradigm of ICT. United Nations. New York and Geneva. Available from http://unctad.org/en/docs/sdteecb20071_en.pdf

¹¹ OECD (2004). The Economic Impact of ICT, Measurement, Evidence and Implications. Available from <http://www.oecd.org/bookshop?pub=922004051P1>

¹² UNCTAD (2010). Information Economy Report 2010: ICTs, Enterprises and Poverty Alleviation. United Nations. New York and Geneva. Available from <http://www.unctad.org/ier2010>

¹³ Intel (2011). The Path to Growth: Accelerating Entrepreneurship and Innovation Through ICT. Available at: <http://www.intel.com/content/dam/www/public/us/en/documents/white-papers/world-ahead-accelerating-entrepreneurship-paper.pdf>

¹⁴ OECD and Eurostat (2005). Oslo Manual: Guidelines for Collecting and Interpreting Innovation Data. Third Edition. Available from <http://www.oecd-ilibrary.org/docserver/download/9205111e.pdf?expires=1472036902&id=id&accname=quest&checksum=595B614F50153D1656E1EA1160FE6E58>

Frascati Manual¹⁵. ICT is widely recognized as a major enabler of innovation: according to a study by OECD, higher ICT use, as measured by the number of web facilities, generally increases the probability of innovation¹⁶. Thereby innovation is an important impact assessment dimension.

- Employment: ICTs have undoubtedly a role in the creation of employment and self-employment opportunities¹⁷. Impacts of ICTs' and related trends' adoption can be direct through growth of the ICT sector and ICT-using industries and indirect through multiplier effects. In economies dependent on ICT, individuals can benefit by having requisite ICT skills, thereby enhancing their opportunities for employment. Arguably, ICT can also lead to loss of employment as a result of task automation.

➤ Social

- Prosperity & Well-being: The consideration of prosperity and well-being as a dimension of impact assessment can be justified by the ICT impacts identified in the fields of poverty alleviation and employment under the economical domain and the field of healthcare quality under the social domain.
- Quality of Education: ICTs may deliver significant educational benefits by providing tools for improving the teaching and learning process. Other possible impacts of ICT in education are improved attitudes to learning, development of teachers' technology skills and increased access of the community to adult education and literacy^{18, 19}, which all potentially raise the quality level of education.
- Quality of Health: Quality of Health is also brought forward as an area, where ICT is expected to bring major benefits. According to the World Health Organization²⁰, e-health, broadly defined as "the use of information and communication technologies (ICT) for health", targets to "improve health by enhancing patient services and health systems". According to

¹⁵ OECD (2002). Frascati Manual: Proposed Standard Practice for Surveys on Research and Experimental Development. Available from <http://www.oecd-ilibrary.org/docserver/download/9202081e.pdf?expires=1472037200&id=id&accname=guest&checksum=062653253D1CC67C0DEA522B04BA02AA>

¹⁶ OECD (2010) Are ICT Users More Innovative? An Analysis of ICT-enabled Innovation in OECD Firms. Available from http://www.oecd-ilibrary.org/economics/are-ict-users-more-innovative_eco_studies-2011-5kg2d2hkn6vq?crawler=true

¹⁷ UNCTAD (2011). Measuring the Impacts of Information and Communication Technology for Development. UNCTAD Current Studies on Science, Technology and Innovation. N ° 3 Available from http://unctad.org/en/Docs/dt1stict2011d1_en.pdf

¹⁸ OECD (2010). Are the New Millennium Learners Making the Grade? Technology Use and Educational Performance in PISA. Available from <http://www.oecd.org/edu/cei/45053490.pdf>

¹⁹ Kozma RB (2005). Monitoring and Evaluation of ICT for Education Impact: A Review. In: Wagner DA et al., eds. Monitoring and Evaluation of ICT in Education Projects: A Handbook for Developing Countries. infoDev. Available from https://www.infodiv.org/infodiv-files/resource/InfodivDocuments_284.pdf

²⁰ WHO (2009). Global Observatory for eHealth 2009 Survey. Available from http://www.who.int/goe/data/global_e-health_survey_2009_en.pdf

ITU²¹, e-health applications include electronic health records, e-telemedicine, m-health (the use of mobile devices such as mobile phones for health purposes), decision-support systems, e-learning and e-journals. OECD²² also cites the use of ICT as enabling complex and networked equipment. The application of ICT in health holds major benefits for provider organizations, patients and medical staff, and thus enhances the quality of healthcare provision. On the other hand, there is no doubt that ICT can also have negative effects on health, for instance, occupational overuse injuries associated with computer use.

- Equity & Inclusiveness: The ease and immediacy of communicating, finding information and accessing services, offered by ICTs, creates particularly beneficial impacts for minority groups and those who are socially disadvantaged²³, thus catering for improved equity and inclusiveness within the social domain.
- Privacy & Security: The effects of ICTs on the privacy and security of individuals and organizations are positive only to the point that the solutions adopted are invulnerable to malicious physical or cyberspace attacks. From that point on, there is a number of adverse impacts, such as commercial losses from denial of service attacks, data loss through theft or corruption and disclosure of confidential data. Far more serious potential negative impacts may arise because of the increasing reliance of critical infrastructure on ICT and the serious consequences of failure²⁴. Hence, privacy and security is a significant dimension of impact assessment.

➤ **Infrastructural**

- Public Safety: Public safety involves “the prevention of and protection from events that could endanger the safety of the general public by means of significant danger, injury/harm, or property damage, such as crimes or disasters (natural or human-made”²⁵. Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) have always played an important role in the public safety domain, providing support in all phases of disaster management, e.g. in preparation, mitigation, response or

²¹ ITU (2010). World Telecommunication/ICT Development Report 2010: Monitoring the WSIS Target – A mid-term review. Available from http://www.itu.int/dms_pub/itu-d/opb/ind/D-IND-WTDR-2010-PDF-E.pdf

²² OECD (2007). Measuring the Impacts of ICT Using Official Statistics. Working Party on Indicators for the Information Society. DSTI/ICCP/IIS(2007)1/FINAL. Available from <http://www.oecd.org/dataoecd/43/25/39869939.pdf>

²³ UNCTAD (2011). Measuring the Impacts of Information and Communication Technology for Development. UNCTAD Current Studies on Science, Technology and Innovation. N ° 3 Available from http://unctad.org/en/Docs/dt/stict2011d1_en.pdf

²⁴ OECD (2008). Shaping Policies for the Future of the Internet Economy. OECD Ministerial Meeting on the Future of the Internet Economy, Seoul, 2008. Available from <http://www.oecd.org/internet/ieconomy/40821707.pdf>

²⁵ Wikipedia – Public safety organizations, https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Public_safety_organizations

recovery. The impacts of the use of ICTs on public safety have more specifically to be sought in the directions of enabling effective management of rescue operations, improving the coordination of human and technical resources, reducing the speed of reactions, supporting the mobility of public safety officers and first responders and providing an accurate view of the circumstances.

- Transport Infrastructure: Information and Communication Technology is rapidly evolving and taking centre stage in every domain of everyday life. The same applies for the transport domain, where ICT is greatly influencing mobility and travel choices, as well as travel experience, attempting to provide safer, smarter and greener transport options, improve transport services and design better transport policies.
- ICT Infrastructure: The ICT infrastructure of the public sector is apparently an aspect that is directly influenced by the introduction and adoption of new technologies. Every investment performed by the public sector enhances its ICT infrastructure and potentially creates the conditions for the development of more powerful applications and enhanced services.
- e-Security: While there are countless benefits associated with the introduction and use of Information and Communication Technologies, there is a down side too. The task of protection of the data and information stored in computers and travelling across the internet has never been so challenging. E-security therefore constitutes a specialized area within the technology impact assessment analysis, which points out that it is not sufficient to adopt and deploy new technologies, but effort has to be placed as well into making the relevant services reliable and secure.

➤ Environmental

- Quality of the Biosphere: The identification of the impacts of ICT on the environment and the quality of the biosphere in particular is a relatively new topic. According to OECD²⁶ positive impacts enumerate the facilitation of dematerialization, whereas negative ones account for greenhouse gas emissions arising from the ICT use, the manufacturing and transport of ICT products and pollution from disposal of e-waste.
- Energy Consumption – Natural Resources Utilization: Relevant to the impact of ICT on the quality of the biosphere are also its effects on energy consumption and the utilization of natural

²⁶ OECD (2009). Measuring the Relationship between ICT and the Environment. Available at: <http://www.oecd.org/internet/ieconomy/43539507.pdf>

resources. Positive effects in this case include the potential to improve the efficiency of a range of energy-using processes and equipment, whereas on the contrary negative ones account for an increased dependence on electrical and other forms of energy.

- Environmental Awareness Creation: The role of ICT on the creation of environmental awareness can only be positive and includes ICT's contribution in climate change monitoring and modelling, the dissemination of information, as well as the administration of carbon-pollution-reduction schemes.

These make up, as already explained, a number of vertical dimensions and are further complemented by a set of horizontal impact assessment dimensions, referring to the extent of application of the identified technology solutions, therefore to whether the former can be applied at the individual, local, regional, national or international level, and to their anticipated influence, the latter being characterised by its type (direct, indirect or non-existent) and its (positive or negative) quality.

On the side of the feasibility, the assessment analysis takes into account aspects such as the existing ICT infrastructure and know-how, the status of the related legislative framework and regulation, the readiness of the stakeholders involved, as well as the political will demonstrated in the specific application **context**. This assessment tries to evaluate the identified solutions against these aspects on an appropriate qualitative scale, as follows:

- Existing Infrastructure
 - Inadequate
 - Sufficient
 - Complete
- Legislative framework and regulation
 - Inadequate
 - With Shortcomings
 - Sufficient

- Stakeholder IT literacy
 - Low
 - Moderate
 - High
- Political Will
 - Inadequate commitment
 - Strong commitment

Attention is drawn to the fact that the conduction of the feasibility assessment analysis as prescribed above, presupposes having a thorough knowledge of the context (local, regional, national or international), in which the application of the identified technology solutions is meant to take place, in order to generate meaningful results.

The innovation identification step employs as well the methods of interviews and focus groups primarily and desk-based research secondarily in order to collect and analyse information on the innovation potential of the identified solutions, while as an output it produces a set of appropriate records.

1.2.6 Scenario Building

A scenario is to be intended as a systematic vision of future possibilities²⁷. Conducting such a foresight research usually means both plausible possibilities as well as others that do not rely on too extreme wild cards. They are used as tools for political or strategic decision-making and to explore the impact of particular decisions or developments in the future²⁸. More specifically, Scenario Building aims to identify uncertain developments in the future and take those uncertainties as elements of the scenario narrative.

This step is anticipated to use as input the previously generated innovation potential records and to leverage brainstorming techniques in order to develop scenarios on the future of the public sector. The selection of the solutions and therefore the technologies that the public sector needs to adopt can then be based on the specification of the most desired and most probable public sector future scenarios.

²⁷ Janssen, M., Duin, P. van der, Wagenaar, R., Blicking, M., Wimmer, M. (2007) Scenario building for e-government in 2020, ACM Proceedings of the 8th annual international conference on Digital government research: bridging disciplines & domains, pp 296 – 297

²⁸ Nekkers, J. (2007) Wijzer in de toekomst: werken met toekomstscenario's. Business Contact.

Regarding the conceptual framework that aims to formulate the visionary scenario exercise, it has to be noted that foresight research comprises many different methods that can be categorised in several ways. According to the classification introduced by Popper²⁹, one may distinguish between a methods' orientation (normative or exploratory), its nature (quantitative or qualitative) and its essence (expert-based, creativity-based, interaction-based or evidence-based) as shown in the following figure.

²⁹ Popper, R. (2008) Foresight methodology. In Eds Georghiou, L, Cassingena, J., Keenan, M., Miles, I., Popper, R. The handbook of technology foresight. Edward Elgar Publishing

In general, the objectives of a foresight exercise and the degree of uncertainty and complexity involved, are the ones that usually guide the selection of methods for each exercise.

In the context of SONNETS, the aim of the scenario building activities is to explore different possible alternative futures regarding the role of the Public Sector in relation to Innovation and Societal Challenges tackling.

For the given topic, both the selected time horizon of this exercise and the interrelationships of different developments affecting it (like rapid ICT developments) make the future quite dynamic, complex and uncertain, with little available evidence that can be used to predict or forecast those futures. Given this lack of evidence and data, it is impossible to use quantitative and evidence-based methods. Courtney et al³⁰ describe this amount and type of uncertainty as a 'level 3', at which a range of different possible futures can be identified, and point 3 types of foresight methods able to accommodate this level: scenario drafting, back casting and early warnings systems. As the latter two approaches are often incorporated into scenario drafting, the method of scenario design is being suggested for the SONNETS framework³¹.

The overall working method takes inspiration and is founded on past scenario building exercises of similar context, which were performed in the past in EC cofounded projects such as FutureEnterprise³² and CROSSROAD³³, and the overall methodological approach is as follows:

1. Analysis of the technologies and trends documented in the previous steps of the framework for determining the developments that can be considered key drivers for the future.
2. Selection of main Key Uncertainties whose realisation will drive the Public Sector to different futures.
3. Conduction of an open crowdsourcing exercise to get feedback regarding the Key Uncertainties with a view on what is probable to happen and on what is desirable to happen.
4. Elaboration of the different factors and of the role of the Public Sector in those scenarios through a dedicated brainstorming session.
5. Drafting the scenarios based on the results acquired from the previous step which denoted the different socioeconomic factors and business related aspects of the future.

Scenario building exercises focus in most of the cases on identifying extreme futures based on a limited set of uncertainty factors. Those are being documented in most of the cases as combinations of different Key Uncertainties, usually into groups of 2 (or in some rare case 3)) which can be graphically represented as vertical axes constructing a two-dimensional area (or a cube, forming a 3-dimensional space in the case of 3 Key Uncertainties).

³⁰ Courtney, H., Kirkland, J., and Viguerie, P. (1997) Strategy under uncertainty, Harvard Business Review, 67-79.

³¹ Scenario writing is a method that is commonly used in research regarding public services and eGovernment (Duin, van der & Huijboom, 2008; Janssen et. al., 2007; Aicholzer, 2005)

³² FutureEnterprise - Road mapping, Research Coordination and Policy activities supporting Future Internet-based Enterprise Innovation - http://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/110910_en.html

³³ CROSSROAD - A Participative Roadmap for ICT Research in Electronic Governance and Policy Modelling - http://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/93842_en.html

Figure 1: Extreme Points in a 3D Scenario Space

As such, scenario-building exercises aim to describe extreme future situations that may become a reality if the world follows the path towards these endpoints. The different extreme Scenarios are set on the edges of the defined space and they describe the conditions that will dominate in such a future (on each of the Key Uncertainties identified above).

Even though this approach is used extensively in various roadmapping exercises (of which the scenario building constitutes an interim step), there are two major weaknesses that have been criticised in the past that have to do a) with the number of key uncertainties as most exercises tend to overdo it, and b) with the overall approach of investigating these scenarios.

With regard to point a), the projects suggest to select various combinations of 2 or at maximum 3 uncertainties, both for reasons of processing, but also for reasons of comprehension, as more than 3 axes are very difficult to be displayed, processed and easily communicated to stakeholders. Such a proposal, is not only limiting the degree of complexity, but also the possibilities to generate unrealistic scenarios (which come as combination of extremes of different axes).

Furthermore, regarding point b), it is noted that the investigation of the extreme points does not offer the expected added value needed to carry on with the definition of the actions required to move forwards, as such extreme situations are highly unrealistic (or too futuristic) and have a relatively low realisation probability. Thus, describing such scenarios does not evidently lead to a set of gaps (which are then transformed into action lines in a roadmap) that stand between the as-is and the to-be situation. This is simply because the unanimously desirable future scenario is not placed on the table, due to the binary logic of these frameworks which focus only on extreme future situations.

SONNETS tries to differentiate itself from this complex approach by adopting a method that is able to take into consideration different Key Uncertainties and then limit down the analysis to the most realistic scenarios. As such, the methodology sequentially tries to investigate the different Probable and Desirable scenarios (coming through a crowdsourced exercise, and therefore not being polarised by experts' opinions). As such, not every possible combination of the selected Key Uncertainties is examined (as this would generate a huge number of scenarios) but focus is placed on what is most likely to happen (Probable Scenarios), and on what seems like an ideal future (Desirable Scenario).

Investigating those different sets, helps to formulate more realistic propositions towards the domain's stakeholders. These will not only uncover future opportunities, but showcase also potential actions that need to be performed to cater for sustainable investments, identifying the shifts that will most likely (need to) happen in the quest of the world becoming a place which is more productive, sustainable and nice to live and work in. In this context, once these scenarios are defined, attention should be turned into the necessary actions that will bring the probable future as close as possible to the desirable one.

Figure 2: Probable Futures and the Desirable one

With regards to the SONNETS Innovation Identification Framework, four Key Uncertainties are proposed, which have been selected for building the different scenarios. These Key Uncertainties do not claim to cover the entire landscape of the future regarding the role of the Public Sector inside an ICT-powered society, but can be taken as a core material to base the main assumption of the different scenarios. As such, they can be complemented with other Key Uncertainties, replaced or disregarded, depending on the context of each application of the framework.

Public Sector Role	Urgency of Societal Needs	Degree of Power Concentration	Operations & Decision Making
Innovation Leader	Prosperity	Centralised Governance	Machine Intelligence
Open Innovation Evangelist	Stability	Hybrid Decision Structures	Knowledge based
Innovation Facilitator	Scarcity	Federated Decision Systems	Crowd Wisdom

The following lines present very briefly the conditions that correspond to each value of the key uncertainties presented above.

- **Key Uncertainty I – Public Sector Role**
 - Innovation Leader. The Public sector is fully modernized, assets are generally openly exposed, PPPs with third party stakeholders are established, big governmental labs push technology, selected population groups are testing novel techs and innovations, intense collaboration with industry, startups and entrepreneurs is taking place.
 - Open Innovation Evangelist. There is a highly modernised Public Sector, novel technologies are adopted soon after they go mainstream, selected assets are openly provided to the public, close collaboration with industry and few enterprises takes place.
 - Innovation Facilitator. Public sector is still a technology laggard, innovations are adopted after widespread adoption and there is a high demand pressure from the public.
- **Key Uncertainty II – Urgency of Societal Needs**
 - Prosperity. Most Needs solved, Fast growth, Natural & human resources in abundance, high average per capita income, fair distribution of wealth, high life expectancy, highly educated societies, long peace.
 - Stability. A 2-speed world with economic, socio-political and environmental sustainability, mix of social classes, average income distribution, micro-conflicts.
 - Scarcity. Societal Needs are still not tackled, shortage of resources, high levels of inequality in income, education and health, polarised social classes, frequent signs of upheaval (riots, medium to high-intensity conflicts).
- **Key Uncertainty III - Degree of Power Concentration**
 - Centralised Governance. Decisions are taken centrally, and management is performed centrally too, leaving no flexibility to grassroots movements and individual innovation.
 - Hybrid Decision Structures. Collaboration between central and federated decision makers, knowhow transfer, leaving central and more strategic decisions to central authorities and implementation to smaller scale organisations, better openness.
 - Federated Decision Systems. Local decisions, smaller scale impact, less openness, competition between federations, innovation silos.
- **Key Uncertainty IV - Operations & Decision Making**
 - Machine Intelligence. Management, operational processes, supporting activities & external communication are based exclusively on machines (Artificial Intelligence and Automation).
 - Knowledge based. Machine-intensive operational and supporting processes, controlled and managed by human intelligence.
 - Crowd Wisdom. Decisions are taken through crowdsourcing and collaboration of community members, tradition plays an important role into making choices, and technology performs only transactional and heavy-duty operations.

1.2.7 Validation

The refined list of innovation solutions and respective technologies, as reflected through the appropriate developed scenarios will eventually provide input for the last step of the framework methodology, targeting the validation of the overall findings. The latter is intended to place these findings under evaluation in order to gather feedback, revise and validate the results. Evaluation and validation in this context are to be performed through specialized workshops, engaging representatives of public authorities, civil society organizations, research institutes and companies, and online public consultations, engaging the general public.

